

WLAN APPLICATION BASED ON A CPW FED DUAL BAND METAMATERIAL ANTENNA

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Abstract:

A CPW fed dual band metamaterial antenna is presented for WLAN Applications. It is composed of a loop loaded periodically with mu-negative transmission line (MNG-TL) and a circular patch located in the center of loop for lower and upper frequency band respectively. The mu negative transmission line loop is based on the infinite wavelength property allows current along the loop for the same magnitude and phase to create omnidirectional radiation pattern. On the other hand, a unidirectional radiation pattern is generated by a circular patch. In order to feed the mu negative transmission line, a CPW transmission line is proposed. Finally, the proposed antenna is fabricated and measured. It is demonstrated that the measurement has good agreement with simulation.

Index Terms: WLAN Applications, Loop Antenna, Metamaterial (MTM), Mu Negative Transmission Line (MNG-TL) & Patch Antenna.

1. Introduction:

Body centric wireless communications have aroused a lot of interests for applications in many communication systems [1][2]. In Body centric communication systems, three communication links including an on-body link, an off-body link, and an in-body link can be constructed and shared by all terminal devices arranged on or in a human body. An on-body link describes the channel between body mounted devices while an off-body link refers to that between body worn devices and base-station units or mobile devices located in surrounding environment. As for an in-body link, it is a communication channel between wireless medical implants and on-body nodes [1]–[3]. Consequently, an antenna which can realize different type of radiation patterns and different polarizations simultaneously on different body surfaces is actually expected. In an on-body link, for instance, an omnidirectional pattern along the human body is desired; whereas a unidirectional beam normal to a human body surface is desired for an off-body communication link. It is noted that most wearable antenna designs including planar dipoles, monopoles, planar inverted-F antennas (PIFAs), and textile microstrip patches with EBG substrate obviously paid more attention to size miniaturization, propagation channel model and the effect of human body presence on the link performance [2], [4]–[8].

Figure 1: Geometry of proposed antenna

To realize an omnidirectional radiation pattern, either an electric monopole and its variety or a magnetic dipole by a small loop with a uniform current distribution could be taken into account. However, for the former, the electric monopole antenna, its profile is confined strictly due to its location on the body for body centric communications. A dual band low profile antenna for body centric communication was proposed [9], in which by a shorted annular ring structure the mode with vertical polarization is excited to provide omnidirectional radiation pattern. But due to the excitation of high order mode, the size of the antenna is somewhat bigger, which may not be suitable for some rigorous situations. It is also the motivation of this letter to improve the performance of our antenna [9].

As we know, a magnetic dipole, small loop antenna, has very small radiation resistance and high reactance inherently, which leads to a poor efficiency and a difficult matching. Consequently, a larger loop antenna possesses a reasonable radiation resistance, but the uniformity of antenna currents distribution along the loop will become poor when the loop radius increases. Hence it could not yield a desired omnidirectional radiation pattern. Another type of loop antenna which can produce omnidirectional pattern with horizontal polarization is Alford loop antenna [10]. Recently, several types of modified Alford loop antennas with a planar structure designed for WLAN applications were proposed [11], [12]. However, the Alford-loop type antenna cannot integrate with other kinds of patch antenna easily and further realize two types of radiation pattern simultaneously due to the restriction on its structure.

On the other hand, the metamaterials (MTMs) [13], [14] have attracted great attention and quickly became the subject of extensive research. Recently, a zeroth-order resonator antenna based on a composite right/left-handed (CRLH) transmission line was investigated in [15] and [16]. A potential advantage of the zeroth-order antenna possesses in its constant phase and constant magnitude field distribution due to zero propagation constant with nonzero group velocity at the zeroth-order resonance. Consequently high efficiency and compact structure can be obtained in the zeroth-order antenna. Inspired by segmented loop antennas, which is composed of a number of metal strip segments periodically loaded with a lumped or distributed capacitor [17], Zhang *et al.* [18] proposed a mu negative transmission line (MNG-TL) loop antenna, a type of zeroth-order antenna, and gave the investigation and theoretical explanation about it using the MNG-TL method.

In this letter, a compact dual-band antenna composed of a loop loaded periodically with MNG-TL and a concentric circular patch is proposed for use in 6 and 12 GHz wireless LAN Applications based on the inspiration aforementioned. Note that this letter, is extended from our initial presentation [19] and more detailed analysis and measured data are presented to verify those results in [19].

2. Analysis and Design:

The geometry of the proposed antenna is shown in Fig. 1. The MNG-TL loop consisting of a number of segments has an inner radius, and an outer radius, is printed on the both sides of a dielectric sheet with relative permittivity, thickness mm and radius mm. The pair of segments printed on the top and bottom sides of dielectric sheet have a half periodicity shift in arrangement. The pair segments can act as a parallel-plate line. In order to realize an in-phase loop current, the loop antenna was loaded with periodic MNG-TL unit cells. The width W of the parallel-plate, the period angle α_1 and the gap angle α_2 . The periodic angle α_1 and the gap angle α_2 are related to the number of cells N by

$$\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 = 2\pi/N$$

In order to make the feed structure convenient and practical, a transition based on a CPW transmission line is proposed. The one terminal of MNG-TL makes transition to a ground of CPW structure and the other one terminal of MNG-TL is transferred to the center strip of CPW. The top and bottom surfaces of CPW ground are connected by metal vias. The gap g between loop outer edge and CPW ground is g and the CPW ground having the angle of will affect the impedance matching. By taking advantage of the remaining space at the center part of an MNG-TL loop, a circular patch with radius is printed on the top of dielectric sheet together with the circular ground plate with radius printed on the bottom surface. Due to the limitation of space, the size of circular ground is generally smaller than that it used to be, when employed in conventional situations. It results in somehow bigger back radiation, which will be shown in following section. HFSS 13.0 is employed here to implement the full wave simulation and optimization [20]. The optimized parameters are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Geometry Parameters

Parameters	Unit(mm)/($^{\circ}$)
r_g	13.5
r_p	9.8
r_s	30
r_a	15
r_b	19.5
g	1
α_1	55
α_2	5
β	32

In order to investigate how the presence of a human-body affects the antenna performance, we simulate the antenna placing on the phantom with relative permittivity and 35.1, conductivity and 3.717 s/m for 2.4 and 5.8 GHz, respectively. In simulation, the circular cylinder tissue model with thickness of 40 mm and radius of 60 mm is employed. The distance between the antenna and the tissue model is changed from 5 to 20 mm [2], [8], [21]. For the low band, the simulated gain in azimuth plane at 2.4 GHz increases from dBi to dBi with increasing distance from 5 to 20 mm as its polarization is parallel to the tissue surface. At the same time the resonant frequency will shift from 2.6 to 2.4 GHz. For the upper band, the effect of a human-body on antenna performance at 5.8 GHz can be negligible due to its polarization is perpendicular to the tissue surface.

3. Experiment and Verification:

A prototype antenna was fabricated and its picture is shown in Fig. 2. Compared to our initial proposed antenna in [9], the outer size is reduced from 11.0 to 6.0 cm.

Figure 2: Prototype of proposed antenna.

The simulated return loss of the proposed antenna is shown in Fig. 3. It is seen that a good agreement is achieved between simulation and measurement. A small frequency shifting is observed at 6GHz band due to the fabrication tolerance.

Figure 3: Simulated return loss of the proposed antenna

The radiation patterns are measured in an antenna chamber. Figure 4 shows the measured normalized Co- and Cross-pol radiation patterns.

Figure 4: Simulated Radiation Pattern

Figure 5: Simulated VSWR

The simulated VSWR of the proposed antenna is shown in figure. The Figure 5 being evidence of VSWR for beyond the required frequency range with VSWR is less than 2.

4. Conclusion:

A dual band antenna composing a loop loaded periodically with mu-negative transmission line (MNG-TL) fed by a CPW structure and a circular patch located in the center of the loop for WLAN Applications has been presented. Radiation pattern has been realized. The simulated results have verified that the proposed antenna yields a good performance while keeps compact size characteristic, which may be a good candidate for application in wireless Local area Network.

5. References:

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